

D3.4 (M18) - Report on developments and operations of the FAIRtracks ecosystem (an ELIXIR Norway ELIXIR₃ deliverable)

Project name: ELIXIR₃ - strengthening the Norwegian Node of ELIXIR

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Context

This report serves as an update on the progress of WP₃ in ELIXIR₃ task 3.5: *"Further development and operations of the FAIRtracks standard for minimal genomic track metadata (functional genomics) and related libraries and services in the FAIRtracks ecosystem"*. The report documents progress made, changes in the scope of the task, and plans for the near future as of month 18 of a 48-month timeline.

Background

The FAIRtracks ecosystem grew out of the needs of the [Genomic HyperBrowser analysis platform](#), whose development on the infrastructure side has been funded in ELIXIR₁, ELIXIR₂, and ELIXIR₃. During this period, we have witnessed an explosion of publicly available datasets describing e.g. aspects of functional processes that relate to particular locations along reference DNA sequences. This type of data can collectively be called "genomic annotations" or simply "genomic tracks" and is the main type of data that can be analysed in the HyperBrowser platform.

It has been clear to us from the very beginning of the HyperBrowser project that there has been a need for harmonised metadata models for genomic track data. Thus, we took the initiative to start an ELIXIR Hub-backed Implementation Study – together with colleagues from the Spanish ELIXIR node and the European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI) in Hinxton, UK – to build a harmonised metadata schema for genomic tracks, with related services. The output of this study was named "The FAIRtracks ecosystem" and was further [accepted as an ELIXIR Recommended Interoperability Resource](#). This is a quality mark from

ELIXIR Europe for services that to a large extent support the FAIR principles by enabling interoperability and reuse of knowledge. Towards the end of ELIXIR₂, the FAIRtracks ecosystem was added to the Service Delivery Plan (SDP)¹ of ELIXIR Norway as an expansion of the previous "GTrack/BioXSD ecosystem". These are services the Norwegian node commits to deliver to the European life science research community. For more information on the background, output and goals of the FAIRtracks project we refer to a [blog post](#) published in F1000Research in Dec. 2021².

Changes in the scope of the task

Just after the finalisation of the ELIXIR₃ application, a major development necessitated a significant change in focus for the FAIRtracks project, and hence task 3.5 in ELIXIR₃. With help from the ELIXIR Hub, the project came in contact with [RDA Europe](#), the "European plug-in to the Research Data Alliance", and was selected as a *pilot* to receive facilitation and other types of practical support from the "[Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions](#)" (RDA TIGER) project, in its application to the Horizon Europe call: "[HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01](#)". The RDA TIGER project was funded and started operation in January 2023. There is, however, no direct funding available for RDA TIGER pilot groups.

Our updated plan is to continue the FAIRtracks development in the context of a larger community as a step towards building a global community standard and infrastructure for the discovery and reuse of genomic track data. We have thus launched an initiative to start a "FAIRification of Genomic Annotation" working group (WG) in the RDA, and it is this initiative that receives support from the RDA TIGER project. In order to raise a level of community interest to justify an RDA working group, we have decided to change the scope and focus of task 3.5 to build towards this goal. In particular, we have focused on:

- Developing a redesigned web portal that can serve both as a resource for raising interest in the RDA WG and also function as a community portal once the WG is set into motion.
- Developing a generic Python library named [Omnipy](#) to simplify the development and deployment of scalable and maintainable metadata transformation/curation pipelines, including (meta)data wrangling and validation capabilities. The aim is that this library will not only cater for our plans to develop pipelines to add content to the [TrackFind service](#) (which is a part of the FAIRtracks ecosystem), but also to international collaborators in the RDA WG, and beyond.

¹ The FAIRtracks ecosystem is also a part of the SDP of ELIXIR Spain.

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- Engagement with researchers and groups doing related work with the goal of raising enough interest to justify an RDA WG on the topic. This includes presentations and posters at relevant conferences and workshops and other efforts to bring focus to our initiative

Due to the change in focus, these subtasks from the ELIXIR3 project plan have been postponed to later in the 48-month period:

- *"Curate existing track repositories for inclusion in TrackFind"*. Instead, our focus has shifted to building general functionality in Omnipy to enable later content addition in a more scalable and maintainable way than was earlier planned.
- *"Further develop and operate a solution for distribution of track data (TrackSpace)"*. This subtask is put on hold as this might not be so important in light of the new strategy. We will, later in the project period, consider whether there is a need to carry out this subtask.
- *"Upgrade the GTrack ecosystem of file formats and libraries for genomic track data and metadata. Evolve core features according to community needs."* This subtask has been postponed and is now planned to be implemented on top of the Omnipy library. The Omnipy library needs to be further developed before it makes sense to begin this subtask.

Delivery

Due to the above-mentioned changes in focus, this deliverable will not contain any developments relating to the following items from the project plan:

- *"Report on added content to TrackFind/TrackSpace respectively with raw/preprocessed functional genomic datasets and FAIRtracks-curated metadata"*
- *"Release of a major upgrade to the GTrack library (GTrack ecosystem)"*

The following item has, however, seen significant development:

- *"Release of libraries and Galaxy integration for search and retrieval (FAIRtracks ecosystem)."*

This feature has been developed into a functioning prototype that is nearing production. Central to this prototype are two proposed new features of the internationally recognised Galaxy analysis framework, in the form of two draft "pull requests" to Galaxy's open-source repository:

- [Interactive Client tools implemented client-side](#)
- [Support for GTrack and GSuite datatypes](#)

An early prototype of this work was presented at:

- [Galaxy Community Conference 2022](#), July 17 2022, Minneapolis, USA
 - Slides: <https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119700.1>
 - Poster: <https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119699.1>
- [The European Galaxy Days](#), Oct 4 2022, Freiburg, Germany
 - Slides: <https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119701.1>

The implemented features allow for the search and retrieval of metadata records that are registered in [TrackFind](#) through a user interface that is embedded in Galaxy. The latest prototype is available for testing at: <https://galaxy.fairtracks.net/>

In line with the changed focus of task 3.5, the following have been delivered:

- The new website of the FAIRtracks project, <https://fairtracks.net>, was implemented (source code: <https://github.com/fairtracks/fairtracks.net/>). The website was designed to be able to evolve into a community portal. Currently, the website contains:
 - Background info about the domain (genomic tracks and their applications)
 - Overview of the FAIR-enabling solutions implemented in the FAIRtracks ecosystem
 - Overview of the metadata schemas and services of the FAIRtracks ecosystem
 - Relevant material (papers, posters, presentations, and more)
 - The website launched in November 2022
- We have developed Omnipy, a new Python library that offers a maintainable and scalable solution to develop and deploy pipelines to transform and validate data and metadata. Omnipy was already under development at the start of ELIXIR3. The library can now be used in practice, but is still lacking some key features and the required polishing for a v1.0 release.
 - The last "pre-release" version of the library before the end of M18 was version [0.10.5](#) from Sep 29, 2023:
 - DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10726882>
 - Update Feb 26, 2024:
 - Last available version of Omnipy is [0.15.8](#):
 - DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10726903>
 - Omnipy is available as a Python installable package at <https://pypi.org/project/omnipy/>
 - The source code is available at <https://github.com/fairtracks/omnipy>

- We have held several workshops at the University of Oslo (UiO) on the concepts behind and the use of Omnipy (initially named "uniFAIR"), additionally supported through add through some local funds from UiO:
 - [Oslo Bioinformatics Week 2022](#), Dec. 9, 2022
 - [Digital Scholarship Days 2023](#), Jan 12, 2023
 - Collection of Omnipy-related events on the ELIXIR Training eSupport System (TeSS)
https://tess.elixir-europe.org/events?include_expired=true&tools=omnipy

Update Feb 26, 2024:

- [Oslo Bioinformatics Week 2023](#), Dec 14, 2023
 - [Digital Scholarship Days 2024 \(part 1 & part 2\)](#), Jan. 8, 2024
- We have further developed and applied Omnipy in the following projects in the ELIXIR-funded Biohackathon Europe:
 - [BioHackathon Europe 2022](#):
 - "Streamlining data brokering from Research Data Management platforms to ELIXIR Repositories"
 - Report: <https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/mwkgf>

Update Feb 26, 2024:

- [BioHackathon Europe 2023](#):
 - Project 14: "Enabling continuous RDM using Annotated Research Contexts with RO-Crate profiles for ISA"
 - Report: <https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/7y2jh>
 - Project 27: "Multi-Repository Data Submission using ISA-JSON"
 - Report yet to be published.
- We have presented the initiative for a "FAIRification of Genomic Annotations" working group in the RDA at several meetings and conferences, including:
 - [Research Data Alliance's 20th Plenary \(RDA P20\)](#) in Gothenburg, Sweden:
 - Presentation at "[Data-driven life science and the RDA](#)", satellite meeting Mar 24, 2023:
 - Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8352043>
 - XXIII International Congress of Genetics, Melbourne, Australia:
 - Poster presentations: July 18 & 21, 2023
 - Poster: <https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119626.1>

- [Global Alliance for Genomics and Health \(GA4GH\) 11th Plenary](#), San Francisco, USA
 - Poster:
<https://assets.swoogo.com/uploads/2925915-650b87cb1337f.pdf>
- [RDA Working group kick-off meetings](#), virtual meetings:
 - Kick-off meeting #1, Sep 12 2023:
 - [Minutes](#)
 - [Slides](#)
 - Kick-off meeting #1, Sep 25 2023:
 - [Minutes](#)
 - [Slides](#)

Update Feb 26, 2024:

- [International Data Week 2023 / RDA's 21st Plenary](#), Salzburg, Austria
 - Host and presenter of a Birds-of-a-Feather session on "[FAIRification of Genomic Tracks](#)", Oct 24, 2023:
 - [Session slides](#)
- The status of the initiative for a "FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG" in RDA is per M18, Oct 1. 2023, still unclear. With support from the RDA TIGER project, we hosted two online kick-off events (see list above), which gathered considerable interest. However, we are working to raise the interest of individuals who are willing to take on a co-chair role together with Sveinung Gundersen, from ELIXIR Norway.

Update Feb 26, 2024:

- There are now four confirmed co-chairs for "FAIRification of Genomic Annotation WG", which is now [registered in the RDA web pages](#) as a working group with status: "Pending submission". This refers to the submission of a "Case statement" document describing the motivation and work plan for a working group. We have finalised a "[Case statement](#)" for the WG and will submit this in a matter of days. This document will be reviewed by the Technical Advisory Board of RDA, as well as undergo public review. We do not anticipate any significant issues will be raised in this process and assume we will be acknowledged as an RDA working group within a month or two. The WG is planned to last for 18 months.
- We have contributed significantly to the specification of a new standard that is in development in the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH): [the refget -](#)

[Sequence Collection standard](#). This work will provide significant benefits to the "FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG" .

Outcomes

This task is building the foundation for a global effort to harmonise metadata, which will begin to be realised in the "FAIRification of Genomic Annotation WG" in the Research Data Alliance. The outcome of this WG can be considered an evolution of the FAIRtracks ecosystem, which has received earlier funding through the ELIXIR₂ project, as well as from the ELIXIR Europe hub. The FAIRtracks ecosystem which in this process will be further harmonised with similar other efforts. The end value of this is to allow researchers to more easily leverage public data sources with genomic annotations through data-driven approaches. Use cases include generating data collections for training AI models and improving the discovery and accessibility of genome annotations from biodiversity projects.

The concrete actions recommended for the rest of the ELIXIR₃ project, based on the current outcomes of this task, are:

- Contribute to a successful output of the "FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG"
- Continue to develop the Omnipy Python library and use this to implement metadata transformation pipelines for populating the TrackFind service
- Reimplement the GTrack library, using Omnipy as the basis.
- Release libraries and Galaxy integration for search and retrieval of track metadata based on the TrackFind service
- Determine whether it still makes sense to follow up on the TrackSpace developments. If so, develop a prototype with basic functionality.